

Original Article

COMPETENCIES REQUIRED FOR EFFECTIVE REWINDING OF ELECTRICAL MACHINES FOR SELF EMPLOYMENT IN THE INFORMAL SECTOR OF ENUGU STATE

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Abstract

The study investigated competencies required for effective rewinding of electrical machines for self - employment in the informal sector of Enugu State. Three specific objectives were structured to guide the study. Accordingly three research questions were posed in line with specific objectives and three hypotheses were tested. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The study was conducted in Enugu metropolis. The population for the study is 1143 artisans in the State. Simple random sampling technique was used to obtain a sample size of 132 respondents. Structured questionnaire developed by the researchers was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts; two from Technology and Vocational Education Department and one from measurement and Evaluation of the Department of Computer and Mathematics Education all from the Faculty of Education, Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT), Enugu. A reliability coefficient of 0.77 was obtained using cronbach alpha method. A total of 120 copies out of 132 copies of the instrument correctly filled and returned were used for the study, representing 90.9 percent return rate. Mean was used to answer the three research questions. The three null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test statistic. The result revealed that artisans require armature, fields and commutating rewinding competencies for rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment in the informal sector of Enugu State. The study further revealed that male and female artisans had uniform opinions on the armature, fields and commutating rewinding competencies for rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment in the informal sector of Enugu State. It was recommended among others that all the identified competencies (armature, fields and commutating rewinding competencies) should be integrated into the curriculum of technical colleges by curriculum planners for training of students.

Keywords: Rewinding, Electrical machines, Self-employment and informal sector

Introduction

The livelihood of the poor in emerging market and developing economies often depend on the informal economic activity. The informal economy in Nigeria plays a significant role in employment generation and poverty reduction. The informal sector of the economy refers to economic activities that are not officially recognized or regulated by the government

(Ekezie & Owo, 2019). These activities are often characterized by a lack of formal structures, legal protections, and government oversight.

The informal sector typically consists of small-scale businesses, self-employment, and household enterprises that operate outside of the formal economy. Workers in the informal sector often do not have access to social security benefits,

employment protections, or stable income streams. In many developing countries, According to Ari (2020), the informal sector plays a significant role in providing employment opportunities and contributing to economic growth. It is estimated that a large portion of the population in these countries is employed in the informal sector, engaging in activities such as street vending, casual labor, domestic work and artisanal production.

Generally, artisans constitute a great percentage of the workforce in the electrical industry (Amatrol, 2020). An artisan is skilled craft worker who makes or creates things by hand. Artisans are also referred to as crafts workers. There are male and female artisans. Thus, artisans are said to possess psychomotor competencies or skills. Psychomotor competency is a competency that borders on manual dexterity and motor skills. Artisans in most cases have little or no theoretical knowledge of their trades (Agbo & Okoye, 2022). There are many skill trades such as electrical/electronics, mechanic, building construction, fine arts among others that are prevalent in Nigeria. These trade areas give rise to various categories of artisans. Artisans are categorized based on their trade. For instance, there are mechanical works artisans, building construction artisans, rewinding of electrical machines among others.

Electrical machines are devices that convert electrical energy into mechanical energy or vice versa. They are fundamental components in various electrical systems and are widely used in a range of applications such as power generation, transportation, industrial processes, and home appliances. There are two main types of electrical machines: generators and motors (Abassah, 2019). Generators (also known as dynamo or alternators) convert mechanical energy into electrical energy by inducing a voltage in a conductor through electromagnetic induction. This process is commonly used to produce electricity in power plants and renewable energy sources like wind

turbines and hydroelectric generators. On the other hand, motors convert electrical energy into mechanical energy, causing motion or rotation. Amatrol (2020) stated that electric motors are utilized in many applications, from powering fans and pumps to driving vehicles and operating machinery. Motors can be categorized into various types based on their construction and operation principles, such as DC motors, AC motors, synchronous motors, and asynchronous motors. Electric machines are designed with specific configurations and components, including stator (stationary part), rotor (rotating part), armature, magnetic cores and winding.

Rewinding of electrical machines involves the repair and replacement of damaged or worn-out components in motors, generators, transformers, and other electrical equipment. According to Owo and Ajie (2020), rewinding of electrical machines involves the repair or replacement of the wire coils or windings on the armature, field winding, or commutator in motors or generators. The process is necessary when the coils become damaged due to wear and tear, overheating, or other factors that degrade their insulation or conductivity. Rewinding helps restore the efficiency and functionality of the machine by replacing the faulty windings with new ones. During the rewinding process, the damaged coils are removed, and new coils are wound in place using the correct wire size, type, and winding configuration (Okwelle & Owo (2022)). This process requires a combination of technical skills and knowledge to disassemble, diagnose, repair, and reassemble the electrical machine. In the context of the informal economy, individuals who engage in rewinding of electrical machines often operate as self-employed artisans, providing their services to local businesses and households. One area within the informal economy that has seen growth is the rewinding of electrical machines. With the increasing demand for repaired or rewound electrical machines in industries, homes, and businesses, there

is a need for individuals to possess the necessary competencies to effectively carry out the rewinding process.

Competency is the standard requirement for an individual to properly perform a specific job. Competency is the ability to possess suitable and sufficient skills, knowledge and experience for carrying out a particular task. Ogbuanya (2019) noted that competency is the knowledge, skills, attitude and judgment which one requires in order to perform successfully at a specified proficiency in any given work. In the context of this study, competency is the capacity of an artisan to rewind electrical machines. The competencies required for rewinding of electrical machines include field, commutating and armature (Ogbuanya, Chukwu and Orji, 2020).

Armature rewinding is the process of replacing the wire coils on the armature of an electrical machine, such as a motor or generator. Over time, the insulation on the coils can deteriorate due to factors such as heat, vibration, or electrical stress, leading to shorts or breaks in the coils (Ademu, Adah and Atsumbe, 2018). When this happens, the armature must be rewound to restore its functionality. During the rewinding process, the old coils are removed from the armature and new coils are wound in their place (Okwelle and Owo (2022). The new coils must be wound with the correct size and type of wire to ensure that the machine operates efficiently and safely. Once the armature has been rewound, it is typically tested to ensure that it meets the required specifications before being reinstalled in the electrical machine.

Field rewinding is the process of replacing the wire coils on the field windings of an electrical machine, such as a motor or generator. The field windings are responsible for producing the magnetic field within the machine, which is essential for its operation (Lawal, 2020). Over time, the insulation on the field windings can deteriorate due to factors such as heat, vibration, or electrical stress, leading to shorts or

breaks in the coils. When this happens, the field windings must be rewound to restore the magnetic field and functionality of the machine. During the field rewinding process, the old coils are removed from the field windings and new coils are wound in their place (Agbo & Okoye, 2022). The new coils must be wound with the correct size and type of wire to ensure that the machine operates efficiently and safely.

Commutating rewinding is a process used to repair or replace the commutator and brushes in a direct current (DC) electric machine, such as a DC motor or generator. According to Okwelle and Owo (2022), the commutator is a rotary switch that ensures the correct direction of current flow in the armature windings, allowing the machine to produce torque. Over time, the commutator can become worn or damaged, leading to issues such as sparking, overheating, or reduced efficiency. Amatrol (2020) stated that commutating rewinding involves removing and replacing the commutator and brushes to restore the machine's performance. Commutating rewinding is an important maintenance procedure to extend the lifespan and improve the performance of DC electric machines. In the context of the informal economy, individuals who engage in rewinding of electrical machines often operate as self-employed entrepreneurs.

Self-employment refers to a situation where an individual creates, begins and takes control of the business decision rather than working for an employer. Ado and Hudu (2018) described self-employment as act of working for oneself. Self-employment is the act of generating one's income directly from customers, clients or other organizations as opposed to being an employee of a business or person. When one is self-employed, it means one is carrying on one's own business rather than working for an employer (Agbo and Okoye, 2022)

In Nigeria's informal economy, self-employment has emerged as a vital avenue for individuals seeking

financial independence and economic stability. The electrical repair industry, particularly in the area of rewinding electrical machines, presents significant opportunities for entrepreneurship (Odika and Tom, 2020). However, there is a notable gap in understanding the specific competencies required for effective rewinding of electrical machines, which hinders the ability of aspiring entrepreneurs to establish successful ventures, leading to sub-par performance, customer dissatisfaction, and ultimately, reduced economic impact. It is therefore worthwhile to identify the competencies required for effective rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment in the informal sector of Enugu State.

Statement of the Problem

The informal economy in Nigeria plays a crucial role in the country's overall landscape, providing employment opportunities and income sources for millions of citizens. According to recent statistics, over 80% of Nigeria's workforce is engaged in the informal sector, which encompasses a wide range of activities that are not regulated by the government. Among these activities, the repair and rewinding of electrical machines, such as generators, transformers, and motors, represent a significant area of self-employment that can be leveraged for economic advancement. To successfully engage in the rewinding of electrical machines, individuals require a specific set of competencies that extend beyond mere technical skills.

Despite the importance of these competencies, there remains a knowledge gap regarding the specific skills and training required for effective self-employment in the rewinding of electrical machines. Many individuals enter this field without sufficient guidance or formal education, relying on informal apprenticeships or trial-and-error methods. However, the lack of formal training and certification programs for electrical machine rewinding in Enugu State has resulted in a shortage of competent and skilled individuals in this field. This has led to poor-quality

repairs, safety hazards, and inefficiencies in the rewinding process. As a result, there is a need to identify the specific competencies required for effective rewinding of electrical machines in the informal economy of Enugu State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the competencies required for effective rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment in the informal sector of Enugu State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the armature rewinding competencies required for rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment.
2. Identify the field rewinding competencies required for rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment.
3. Ascertain the commutating rewinding competencies required for rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What are the armature rewinding competencies required for rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment?
2. What are the field rewinding competencies required for rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment?
3. What are the commutating rewinding competencies required for rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Ho1: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and artisans on the armature rewinding competencies required for rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment.

Ho2: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female artisans on the field rewinding competencies required for rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment.

Ho3: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female artisans on the commutating rewinding competencies required for rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment.

Method

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The study was conducted in Enugu metropolis. The population for the study is 1143 artisans in the State. A purposive sample size of 132 was used for the study. Structured questionnaire developed by the researcher was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts; two from Technology and Vocational Education Department and one from measurement and Evaluation of the Department of Computer and Mathematics Education all from the Faculty of Education, Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT), Enugu. The questionnaire used four-point rating scale with response options namely; Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). To determine the reliability of the instrument, the researcher administered 20

copies of the questionnaire to 20 artisans in Anambra State. A reliability co-efficient of 0.77 was obtained using cronbach alpha method. A total of 120 copies out of 132 copies of the instrument correctly filled and returned were used for the study, representing 90.9 percent return rate. Mean was used to answer the three research questions. Any mean score of 2.50 and above was regarded as Agree while items with mean score below 2.50 were regarded as Disagree. The three null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test statistic. When the calculated t-value was equal to or greater than the critical value at appropriate degree of freedom, the null hypothesis was significant and rejected but when the t-calculated value was less than the critical value, the null hypothesis was not significant, and not rejected.

Results

Research QuestionOne

What are the armature rewinding competencies required for rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment?

Table 1: Mean Ratings of the respondents on the armature rewinding competencies required for rewinding of electrical machines

S/N	Armature rewinding competencies include abilities to:	Male artisans			Female artisans		
		\bar{X}	SD	RMKS	\bar{X}	SD	RMKS
1	select appropriate gauge and type of wire for rewinding	3.00	0.65	A	2.52	0.57	A
2	identify and remove damaged coils	2.71	0.62	A	2.55	0.58	A
3	calculate number of turns for each coil	2.68	0.88	A	2.57	0.60	A
4	insulate and secure coils properly	2.55	0.70	A	3.01	0.60	A
5	connect coils to commutator or slip rings	3.11	0.52	A	2.58	0.59	A
6	balance armature after rewinding	2.60	0.54	A	2.50	0.61	A
7	perform inter-turn and ground fault testing	2.70	0.83	A	2.71	0.59	A
Grand Mean		2.76	0.67	A	2.63	0.59	A

Data presented inTable1shows that the mean ratings of male artisans and rangesfrom2.55to3.11 and female artisans 3.01 to 2.58which indicated that the respondents agreed that the aforementioned items are the armature rewinding competencies required for

rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment in the informal sector of Enugu State.

Hypothesis One

HO₁: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female artisans on the armature rewinding competencies required for

rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment.

Table 2: The t-test analysis of mean ratings of the respondents on armature rewinding competencies required for rewinding of electrical machines

Group	N	X	SD	df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Male teachers	91	2.76	0.67	29	1.21	1.96	Ho not rejected
Female artisans	29	2.63	0.59				

Data analyzed in Table 2 shows that the calculated t-value at 0.05 level of significance and 118 degree of freedom is 1.21, while the table value is 1.96. Therefore, the null hypothesis was not rejected. This implies that male and female artisans did not differ significantly in their opinions on the armature rewinding competencies required for rewinding of

electrical machines for self-employment in the informal sector of Enugu State.

Research Question Two

What are the fields rewinding competencies required for rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment?

Table 3: Mean Ratings of the respondents on the fields rewinding competencies required for rewinding of electrical machines

S/N	Fields rewinding competencies include abilities to:	Male artisans			Female artisans		
		\bar{X}	SD	Rmks	\bar{X}	SD	Rmks
1	identify and removing damaged field coils	2.66	0.65	A	2.52	0.57	A
2	correct wire gauge and number of turns	2.61	0.52	A	2.53	0.58	A
3	insulate field coils properly	2.68	0.88	A	3.44	0.69	A
4	connect field coils to the appropriate terminals	3.53	0.71	A	2.50	0.60	A
5	repair shorted field coils	3.39	0.51	A	2.51	0.57	A
6	ensure proper alignment of field poles	2.60	0.54	A	2.50	0.61	A
7	balance field coils	2.65	0.83	A	2.63	0.59	A
Grand Mean		2.87	0.66	A	2.66	0.60	A

Data presented in Table 3 shows that the mean ratings of male artisans' and female artisans ranges from 2.50 to 3.44 which indicated that the respondents agreed that the aforementioned items are the field rewinding competencies required for rewinding of electrical machines for self-

employment in the informal sector of Enugu State.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female artisans on the field rewinding competencies required for rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment.

Table 4: The t-test analysis of mean ratings of the respondents on field rewinding competencies required for rewinding of electrical machines

Group	N	X	SD	df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
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Male teachers	91	2.94	0.66				Ho	not
Female teachers	29	2.76	0.60	118	1.29	1.96	rejected	

Data analyzed in Table 4 showed that the calculated t-value at 0.05 level of significance and 118 degree of freedom is 1.29, while the table value is 1.96. Therefore, the null hypothesis was not rejected. This implies that male and female artisans did not differ significantly in their opinions on field rewinding competencies required for rewinding of electrical

machines for self-employment in the informal sector of Enugu State.

Research Question Three

What are the commutating rewinding competencies required for rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment?

Table 5: Mean ratings of the respondents on the commutating rewinding competencies required for rewinding of electrical machines

S/N	Commutating rewinding competencies include abilities to:	Male artisans			Female artisans		
		\bar{X}	SD	RMKS	\bar{X}	SD	RMKS
15	identify and remove damaged commutator segments	3.41	0.61	A	3.11	0.53	A
16	clean and polish commutator surface	3.53	0.72	A	3.40	0.50	A
17	inspect brushes and brush holders	3.49	0.63	A	3.06	0.46	A
18	repair or replace damaged commutator bars	3.53	0.53	A	3.15	0.48	A
19	replace worn brushes	3.26	0.69	A	3.37	0.59	A
20	ensure proper alignment of commutator with armature shaft	3.51	0.50	A	3.30	0.56	A
21	troubleshoot sparking issues	2.55	0.70	A	3.01	0.60	A
Grand Mean		3.46	0.61	A	3.23	0.52	A

Data presented in Table5 reveals that the respondents agreed that the aforementioned items are commutating rewinding competencies required for rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment in the informal sector of Enugu Stateas indicated in grand mean scores of 3.46 and 3.23.

Hypothesis Three

HO₃: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female artisans on the commutating rewinding competencies required for rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment.

Table 6: The t-test analysis of mean ratings of the respondents on the commutating rewinding competencies required for rewinding of electrical machines

Group	N	X	SD	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Dec.
Male	91	3.45	0.68				Ho
Female	29	3.24	0.51	118	1.20	1.96	not rejected

Data analyzed in Table 6 shows that the calculated t-value at 0.05 level of significance and 118 degree of freedom is 1.20, while the table value is 1.96.

Therefore, the null hypothesis was not rejected. This implies that male and female artisans had similar views on the commutating rewinding competencies

required for rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment in the informal sector of Enugu State.

Discussion of the Findings

The results of the analysis of research question one revealed armature rewinding competencies required for rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment in the informal sector of Enugu State. These competencies are ability to select appropriate gauge and type of wire for rewinding, ability to identify and removing damaged coils, ability to calculate number of turns for each coil, ability to balance armature after rewinding and ability to perform inter-turn and ground fault testing. The findings are in consonance with that of Adem, Adah and Atsumbe (2018) who reported that acquisition of appropriate competencies required for rewinding of electrical machines is the prerequisite in the preparation of students for job creation and self-reliance. The corresponding hypothesis revealed that male and female artisans did not differ significantly in their opinions on the armature rewinding competencies required for rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment in the informal sector of Enugu State. The result of the study depicts that gender has no influence on the responses of the respondents.

In addition, evidence from analysis of research question two showed that fields rewinding competencies are required for rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment in the informal sector of Enugu State. This finding is in line with Ogbu (2019) who noted that acquisition of installation and maintenance skills of electrical machines as offered in technical colleges prepares an individual with job-satisfying requirements towards employment and self-reliance. This is in harmony with the findings of Okwelle and Owo (2022) who stated that practical skills like ability to solder copper and iron pipes, ability to use manifold gauge to charge electrical machines and ability to dismantle and reassemble a reciprocating compressors and

likes are highly required for effective installation and repair of electrical machines for sustainable self-employment of electrical/electronics technology education graduates. The corresponding hypothesis revealed male and female artisans did not differ significantly in their opinions on fields rewinding competencies required for rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment in the informal sector of Enugu State. The implication is that gender has no influence on the responses to the itemized mechanical system competencies.

Data analyzed with regard to research question three indicated that commutating rewinding competencies are required for rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment in the informal sector of Enugu State. The findings of this study are in line with Agbo and Okoye (2022) who determined the commutating rewinding competencies needed for self-employment in rewinding of electrical machines. Agbo and Okoye specifically found that, in rewinding of electrical machines, competencies such as ability to clean and polish commutator surface, ability to repair or replace damaged commutator bars and ability to ensure proper alignment of commutator with armature shaft among others, are required for self-employment. The corresponding hypothesis revealed that male and female artisans had similar views on the commutating rewinding competencies required for rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment in the informal sector of Enugu State. The result of the study depicts that gender has no influence on the responses of the respondents.

Conclusion

Based on the findings made, the following conclusions were drawn. It can be concluded that artisans require armature, field and commutating rewinding competencies for rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment in the informal sector of Enugu State. The study further revealed that male and female artisans had uniform opinions on the armature, fields and commutating rewinding

competencies for rewinding of electrical machines for self-employment in the informal sector of Enugu State.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

1. All the identified competencies (armature, fields and commutating rewinding competencies) should be integrated into the curriculum of technical

colleges by curriculum planners for training of students.

2. Industrial visits/field trips should be made compulsory in all artisans-based areas in Nigeria.

3. The industries should collaborate effectively with Nigerian technical colleges in the training and supervision of students so as to produce graduates with relevant work competencies.

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